

LATINO EDUCATION DISPARITIES AND EFFECTS ON LATINO CHILD MENTAL
HEALTH

by

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Abstract

This study examines the current state of Latino education and mental health disparities in public elementary schools and aims to develop a framework, which schools can utilize to offer culturally relevant services to students and their families. The framework focuses on the roles of student cultures, identities, and families throughout their academic journey. Methods consisted of interviews with teachers and therapists around cultural issues being addressed by schools, programs which could help bridge the gap of underutilized mental health services, and funding issues. The collected data suggests that culture can be used as a primary asset of relating services and curriculum to students, allowing them an opportunity to feel better represented in what is being taught in public schools. Similarly, mental health resources and activities which appeal to student cultures grant families access to services which now can better relate to past experiences and cultural ideals. The study found that a framework that holds culture at the forefront can create an environment which students can relate to, while the entire family is offered mental health services which are relevant to their cultural ideals and life experiences.

Introduction

The Latino experience in elementary classrooms has generally consisted of lessons that do not directly prove relevant to students' own lived experiences. Historically, Latino students have not received an equal number of resources in schools as compared to their white counterparts. Even today, elementary schools throughout the entire country face different levels of funding, and thus different levels of resources are available to their students. As a direct result from funding differences among schools, students who attend underfunded schools are negatively affected as they face a school experience with a lack of resources provided to them.

Because of this, Latino students face disparities in mental health services which can be offered by schools.

The Latino population is becoming one of the largest within the United States (Rivera-Batiz 1), and as the population continues to grow, so do the challenges in education when compared to other ethnic groups. Latino student achievement among public schools is substantially below the country's average (Rivera-Batiz 2), and to combat this trend, it is imperative that schools begin to cater to the Latino experience to create a positive school setting which best allows Latino elementary students to succeed. To provide such a setting, there is a growing need for schools to implement student culture into the classroom. The Latino experience can be appealed to within the elementary school system by approaching curriculum through a cultural lens, prioritizing the backgrounds and needs of each student.

To better understand the current Latino experience in Southern California public schools and the gravity of the unmet needs that students and their families face, an extensive literature review was conducted to determine the issue at a general level. Additionally, interviews were conducted to understand the issue at a more in-depth level, to understand how a framework can be successfully implemented into elementary schools. The purpose of this project is to examine the development of a framework built on student identity, establishing a school community using multicultural perspectives and family involvement, with the school acting as a hub to provide needed health resources for families to succeed.

Literature Review

This review serves as an analysis of current literature surrounding education disparities among Latino students and the overall impact that the Latino experience in public classrooms has on the students' and families' overall mental health. While the Latino population in the United States continues to increase, so do the challenges Latinos face in education as compared to other ethnic groups. Latino student achievement among public schools is substantially below the country's average (Rivera-Batiz 2). This literature review further investigates Latino education disparities and ultimately outlines how differences in school experiences affect a Latino child's mental health.

Latino Education Disparities

Articles within this literature review regarding Latino education disparities offer insight into different dimensions of the current issue, such as gender differences, quality of education, and physical fitness. Colon and Sanchez investigate the gender disparity faced within Latino education as students travel in between two cultures, their home and dominant societal culture. The article centers around the impacts that acculturation, gender, and the value of education has on educational achievement among Latinos. One key point that the study found is biculturalism's positive impact on academic achievement.

The study explains that Mexican American adolescents who identify with both cultures equally have better educational attainment and academic achievement than students who do not share a bicultural outlook (Colon & Sanchez 254). This research offers great insight into the topic of the Latino experience in classrooms, describing how vital biculturalism is to a student's

performance in school, and how appealing the implementation of student culture can be within a classroom setting.

The study goes on to examine the educational achievement of children from a range of identities regarding gender, cultural familiarity, and economic standing. Colon and Sanchez consider several factors in their research to determine what conditions allow for the best possible academic performance among students. A student's cultural familiarity, gender, and family's economic background all impact a student's achievements (Colon & Sanchez 254), citing the 'Economic value of education', which is the level of belief students have in a good education providing them with higher-paying jobs (Colon & Sanchez 255). By relating to this concept, Latino students place a higher economic value on their education, which reflects the importance of the need to ensure students can succeed in a classroom which is most relevant to their own lives. Due to economic background, many families place a high value on their education as a means of being able to contribute to their family's income.

By relating to the overall Latino experience, schools are able to provide students with an educational experience that is relevant to their own lives and emphasizes student success. The study found that biculturalism is linked to higher GPA (Colon and Sanchez 263), which suggests that by introducing a multicultural perspective into the classroom, students from various backgrounds are better set up to succeed as they learn in a setting which is relevant to their lived experiences. By relating to their findings, one can determine that an ideal learning environment for Latino elementary students is one where each student is represented, and activities are built to embrace student background and culture.

The research of Rivera-Batiz looks at the relationship environment has on educational outcomes within the Latino population. As Latino students show lower educational attainment

when compared to other ethnic groups, the study explains that these disparities are related to the environment in which students live. Latino students face lower educational attainment, enrollment rates, literacy skills and overall achievement and Rivera-Batiz's research concludes that these results can be explained by the difference in students' socioeconomic background, family involvement, and quality of schools (Rivera-Batiz), which follows a similar socioeconomic approach as the previous study of Colon and Sanchez, emphasizing the economic value of education that family background places on a student's academics. Most notably, as Rivera-Batiz's study argues, quality of education holds the strongest role in disparity and is one of the most underlying issues that surround today's school systems. When compared to the overall population, Latino students are not typically enrolled in schools with the most resources available to them, thus adding onto education disparities faced.

The study offers empirical data that is used to explain education disparities among Latino elementary-level students. The article cites percentages of the Latino population in relation to the entire United States, dividing percentages in terms of educational attainment levels. Looking at this, one finds that Latino proficiency rates in math begin to decline from fourth to twelfth grade, while reading proficiency increases during this time. Referencing the study's findings, to improve proficiency rates among Latino students, it is important that schools be able to provide relevant curriculum that are in line with student's backgrounds, fitting lessons, and activities into what are familiar to the students, rather than relating activities to a general majority.

The final article regarding Latino education disparities describes physical education instruction that Latino students face in school. In this study, Sanchez-Vaznaugh provides insight into the physical health of Latino students, which is shaped through physical education, by focusing on how Latino student fitness levels compare to their white counterparts. The study

finds that “school district compliance with PE policies may have the potential to influence Latino children’s fitness patterns” (Sanchez-Vaznaugh 6); by analyzing the relationship between expected fitness levels of Latino students and the policy compliance levels in their schools, research examines the impact on student health that schools can have. The study found that among 48 California school districts, which consisted of 64,073 Latino fifth graders, only 23 of these districts were compliant with Physical education policies and instruction, meaning only 16% of Latino fifth graders attended schools in compliant districts, where adequate PE instruction was delivered (Sanchez-Vaznaugh 4). These findings display the low rate of which Latino elementary students in California experience an adequate physical education based on California Physical Education policy.

In this study of the overall difference of Latino fitness regarding physical education policy, Sanchez-Vaznaugh’s research provides insight to the health implications within the Latino elementary school experience. The findings show a disparity in positive health education being provided to students in these districts by looking through a socioeconomic lens. Acknowledging the study’s central idea, that “school district compliance with PE policies may have the potential to influence Latino children’s fitness patterns” (Sanchez-Vaznaugh 6), it is imperative that schools emphasize the proper delivery of PE instruction to ensure positive student health. As Latino children attend schools which do not provide students with adequate PE instruction, students are not able to establish healthy fitness patterns to maintain a healthy lifestyle, being at a disadvantage to maintain their physical wellbeing. Ultimately this physical component contributes to the overall health disparities that Latino students are facing.

Latino Child Mental Health

Latino mental health has become one of the largest concerns among students due to societal and structural challenges that the overall Latino community face when compared to white students. As these rates rise, Latino students do not receive a sufficient level of needs being met in terms of receiving mental health services. Benjamín Cook researches the overall Psychiatric differences between Latino immigrants and U.S-born Latinos. The study follows six possible pathways that could result in psychiatric disorders: discrimination, family conflict, ethnic identity, satisfaction with economic opportunities, U.S social standing, and neighborhood safety (Cook 2250). All possible pathways are aspects which impact the Latino student experience, which can have lasting effects on their mental health.

The study found that as Latino immigrants spend their lives in the United States, they are at an augmented risk for psychiatric disorders (Cook 2252). While enduring the process of acculturation, Latino students not only undergo high levels of stress when faced with the conflict of home culture and the dominant culture in school, but throughout their entire lives as they develop. Having a bicultural identity thus allows students to be better safeguarded from developing psychiatric disorders (Cook 2251), as they can better navigate cultural differences and be able to function in both cultures. To this point, it is important that schools nurture student's identity development in this regard, allowing the classroom to be a space that encourages the continued development of their home cultures while also being able to become fluent in the dominant host culture, which is an applicable path for both immigrant and U.S born Latino students.

Tania Maria Caballero's research focuses heavily on the overall mental health needs among Latino families. A very important aspect of the mental health issue surrounding Latino

families is the lack of help which parents seek for both themselves and for their children. The study investigates the difference in unmet needs of Latino children when compared to their white counterparts, while also considering self-esteem, family dysfunction, and social adjustments as factors pertaining to family health implications (Caballero, et. al 649). These unmet mental health needs of Latino children are one of the largest issues facing the community, and as the study found, is one that is stuck behind language and cultural barriers. Parents with limited English proficiency are less likely to seek medical screenings for their children (Caballero, et. al 649). Because of cultural barriers within the medical field, the research calls for more linguistically and culturally competent physicians who can properly care for Latino families and ensure their strong health.

As institutions, it is important that Latino families receive adequate access to mental health visits, where information and treatment are given with full consideration and cultural understanding, beginning first with treatment in families' home language. However, outside of the physician's immediate responsibilities, often Latino parents are weary to seek help for mental health issues due to cultural stigmas surrounding mental health overall (Caballero, et. al 652). In cases like this, the response should be education; parents should be given the opportunity to learn about why mental health is important and why Latino children should receive treatment for any concerns. Education can be provided at both the physician's level, but schools also hold a responsibility to provide this information to parents to ensure students' health in the classroom.

The research of Audra Langley tackles the issues related to community engagement and the feasibility of mental health programs offered in elementary schools. The study is based on the responses from six total focus groups: four of the groups consist of educators, one of Spanish-speaking parents, and one of English-speaking parents. The study brings up the importance of

implementing school-based services to reach underserved Latino youth. The study found that first, for any program to work, total buy-in from parents, administrators, and teachers is required (Langley 250). Though these resources would become immediately more accessible from such a program beginning, it would not be sustainable without complete commitment.

A successful program is one that promotes community engagement that educates parents to reduce cultural stigmas surrounding mental health (Langley 259). Parents reported that success in the program was determined by educators building trusting relationships within the school community, while prioritizing mental health care and confidentiality (Langley 259). Parental involvement is determined by the positive impact that educators have on such a program, but group responses offer indications that a program that both educates parents on mental health, while making care more accessible to families is overall positive and achievable. Aside from the actual components of the program itself which is provided to students and families in support of mental health, the program's most important factor for success is in the ability to be built around current-standing relationships between educators and parents, and how these relationships can continue to be built through the program.

In the research done by Cynthia Lopez, an examination of current literature was conducted to further discuss the disparities and barriers which affect Latino utilization of mental health services. Again, the main reasons for underutilization among Latinos are due to language and cultural issues. As the study points out, the language barrier is drastic as there are not many Spanish-speaking physicians, psychiatrists, or therapists available for these underserved communities to seek help from (Lopez 140). Language barriers prevent Latino families from receiving proper care needed. Even if families are open to seeking help, a lack of culturally competent physicians prevent them from receiving treatment that is relevant to their lived

experiences, both in language and cultural differences. The article also examines the parental perceptions of mental health that Latino parents hold, which are in line with cultural stigmas surrounding the topic.

Analyzing cultural stigmas, a questionnaire done by Yeh et. al, shows that Latino parents reported significantly fewer barriers to receiving care, yet this was disproportionate to the reported rate of unmet needs which Latino communities are facing (Yeh et. al). The high rate of unmet needs, despite the parental perception of there being no barriers to access, signifies the substantial effect that cultural stigmas on mental health have on utilization rates. The disregard of Latino children's mental health needs by parents, seeing mental health as non-existent, or insignificant, places Latino youth at a health concern, as they are unable to receive needed mental health care due to parent's cultural biases towards mental health. This represents another component which contributes to the lack of utilization is the lack of access to healthcare. Ultimately, socioeconomic, and cultural factors contribute to the parental perceptions of mental health needs which determine the current rates of underutilized mental health services.

Conclusion

Throughout this literature review, eight articles were examined which describe the current education and mental health disparities among the Latino child population. Issues that are brought up in this review provide insight into how the Latino experience in elementary schools differs from their white counterparts in terms of academic achievement, available resources, and the overall impact these factors have on Latino child mental health. Findings within these articles support the need for a program within schools which promotes student culture and identity in

classrooms, while also prioritizing family involvement and providing health resources to families.

Methods

To collect information on the vital components of a successful framework to address students' unmet mental health needs, this study consisted of 4 semi-structured interviews: two with educators and two with licensed therapists, all of whom serve the Latino community. Interviews were conducted via Zoom and were recorded for further analysis. Interviews typically lasted between 30-45 minutes and consisted of 5 open-ended questions. The following questions were asked of each participant:

- What, if any, unmet needs of Latino elementary students do teachers and therapists feel schools are not addressing?
- What needs are schools doing a good job addressing?
- How can schools bridge the gap between Latino parents and the underutilization of mental health services?
- What programs can schools implement to provide Latino students with effective mental health resources?
- How do you think these programs could be funded, keeping in mind school budget restraints?

Responses were recorded and inputted into a spreadsheet according to participant and question. Data was then coded, following the Descriptive Analysis approach (Saldaña), where

each participant’s responses were grouped together by question and further examined to uncover shared themes found within all responses throughout all interviews.

Results

Unmet Needs	Met Needs	Bridging the Gap	Possible Programs	Funding
Lack of culturally competent programs	Bilingual programs	Parent Education	Enrichment Days	Possible Grants
Lack of SEL opportunities	Parent-led DEI groups	Communication	Student Workshops	LCAP
Lack of accommodating neurodivergence	On-site services (Free breakfast & lunch, counselor, Family Coordinator)	Family Coordinator	Parent Workshops	
Lack of family services				

Unmet Latino Student Needs

When asked to describe the current unmet needs that Latino elementary students are facing in schools, the first issue that participants reported is the lack of culturally competent and sensitive programs offered within elementary schools. Responses suggested that current curriculum does not reflect student cultures, nor do school programs and provided services, both social and health. One therapist in their interview argued, “Curriculum is not allowing students to find their cultural space”, to that point, student identity is not allowed spotlight during school

days. Instead, curriculum consists of a restricted perspective in lessons, which do not relate to the experiences of Latino students.

Participants also cited a current lack of opportunity for socioemotional learning. Not enough time is given throughout the day which allows students to play and be given breaks from testing-centered coursework. Participants saw Socioemotional learning as an important way of connecting teaching emotional literacy and strong mental health practices to curriculum, which students can learn through being active in non-academic social activities during school. Participants emphasized implementing play-oriented learning which integrates student culture into the activities.

Another unmet need shared in participant responses mentioned was the current lack of accommodation of neurodivergent students and their families. Participants cited that the process for parents to reach out to schools about their children is overcomplicated and contains many obstacles that keep parents from understanding the steps to take with neurodivergent students. As shared by one participant, schools do not communicate the steps with parents well in establishing an Individualized Education Program (IEP) for neurodivergent students, in a way which ensures families are provided with the support that allows their students to succeed in the classroom. Families are left in the dark when trying to understand the steps to take to coordinate with teachers in creating a classroom environment which accommodates neurodivergence.

This participant went on to say, “If you don’t say the words, you feel like there’s no help”, that unless a parent actively asks for schools to begin the IEP process, that minimal progress will be made in the establishment of a program. Schools are not providing enough information to parents about scheduling meetings to discuss IEP’s and are not explaining overall processes well enough to ensure the success of students. Based on this experience, schools are

not creating opportunities for families to seek guidance in creating an IEP for their students in a timely manner. By not allowing this to be a productive and prompt process, neurodivergent students are left at a disadvantage when an IEP is not set to accommodate student needs in the classroom.

Another significant unmet need cited by participants is the lack of family services which are being provided by schools. The most reported were the inadequate before and after school programs and childcare services within schools, that reflect a lack of accommodation to parent's work and daily schedules. It is very difficult for many parents to organize their morning and afternoon schedules to ensure that their students can be at home or school on time, and with meals ready, if necessary, when parents need to work and take care of younger children. Lack of such programs also do not benefit those without reliable transportation. Other programs described involved a lack of teaching parents to use technology required for student's homework, school announcements, and overall communication.

Participants also reported a high need for schools directing parents to resources that are available to them and their families, including health, social, and economic resources. This could range anywhere from food insecurity, dentists, eye doctor appointments, and doctor visits, which participants agreed can be conducted at school. Participants considered schools to have a very important role in ensuring parents have adequate access to resources which promote family health and student success.

Latino Student Needs Currently Being Met

When asked to describe current needs that are being addressed by schools, participants described the success of bilingual programs such as Dual Immersion, which they saw as an

excellent way to incorporate home language, while nurturing two languages in classrooms. Participants acknowledged the benefit that this reinstated program has in developing both languages, as opposed to past programs which typically utilized students' home languages in lessons as a transition to fully English classrooms. Participants described Dual Immersion as an opportunity for students to embrace and share their cultures throughout their school years. It is important to acknowledge that certain districts which have a Dual Immersion program are still white-centered, as participants cited that parent meetings would be conducted in English, where Spanish-speaking parents are forced to use translating devices. In cases like these, participants emphasized the importance of catering to both Spanish and English-speaking families in Dual Immersion programs equally.

Participants also described the success of parent-led Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) groups within schools, which promote the embracing of student cultures through cultural clubs and events. The success of DEI groups is reflected in the acknowledging and teaching of cultural practices among student cultures, which are being promoted in public and inclusive school events. The increasing number of teachers of color also promote representation within schools, which benefit student views of attainable goals. While also providing a more culturally relevant experience.

In terms of onsite programs which schools provide, participants reported the success of free breakfast and lunch programs, which have begun to now be offered to all students in recent years. Also, in some districts, the availability of onsite mental health services as therapists, group sessions, and safe common rooms provided to students which promote wellness and positive student health within schools, were discussed for being successful in benefitting students by all participants. Taking into consideration the difference in funding levels between participant

school districts, there is a discrepancy between the level of available onsite mental health services shared within responses. However, there were positive responses shared by participants from districts who are able to provide students with adequate onsite services.

The most positive program within schools which participants cited, was a Family Coordinator office, which directs all families to resources available to them. The success of such an office is through the communication with families that ensures that all needs can be met while keeping costs to families minimal, keeping in mind families with and without insurance. However, responses acknowledged difficulties with families who refuse certain resources based on stigmatized ideas of shame regarding mental health.

Bridging the Underutilization Gap

To bridge the utilization gap among Latino families, all participants first reported the importance of removing the barriers of shame regarding mental health. Little education on mental health within the Latino culture prevents families from understanding the relevance of positive mental health practices in ensuring Latino child health. Participants results revealed the importance of educating parents to understand why their students need mental health services. Participants provided possible methods of educating parents as parent workshops, emphasizing such topics of ‘Intergenerational Trauma’, ‘Understanding Trauma and Emotion’, and ‘What lies Underneath Anger’. During their interview, one therapist emphasized, “Everything starts at home”, a positive home life is one of the most important aspects to ensure student success and health. Parent education is a way to strengthen parental involvement and positive emotional development at home.

Parent education also relies on communication between schools and families. Participants defined successful parent education programs as one that clearly communicates the need for therapy and its true purpose. It is important that schools clearly communicate to parents that student participation in therapy sessions through schools are not done to “get the parent in trouble or call a child ‘crazy’”, instead emphasis needs to be put on the mental health and positive practices of students. Educator and therapist responses agreed on the point that it is essential to relay to parents that these are very real emotions that students are going through.

From interviews, another positive way of bridging the gap is by implementing teams within schools, consisting of educators and therapists, which focus on student mental health. As explained by one educator with a similar team in their school: teams begin with teachers, who when a need is noticed, refer families to the Family Coordinator office, where families can then be directed to necessary resources offered both by the school or through partner non-profit organizations. It is important to note, that many times families would deny any issues that students may have due to held stigmas of shame, but the participant reported that continued parent education on mental health led and making available resources more known to families allows for higher rates of utilization.

Resources provided are dependent on the level of need, and if families have insurance or not. A Family Coordinator office can provide families with no insurance or students with a lower need for in-house therapy sessions. Those with higher needs or families with insurance are referred to partner programs. Per one educator’s experiences within their school, a Family Coordinator office has proven successful in both informing and referring parents to needed resources.

Possible Programs

Responses substantiated an overall theme of implementing culturally competent programs which enrich overall learning. A positive proposed program, which in one therapist's experiences working with schools, are Enrichment Days, which consist of cultural appreciation and reimagined mental health programs. Culture is represented through school wide activities which grant students the opportunity to share aspects of their cultures with the entire school. One therapist described an instance where students performed Baile Folklórico during an assembly. In terms of reimagining mental health, activities should prioritize socioemotional learning, and students actively engaging with their own emotions. As said in their interview, "Teaching mental health is not simply teaching happiness or sadness but allowing students to feel these emotions". Positive ways to achieve this, reported by responses, is through improv or drama classes; activities which emphasize imagination, creativity, and movement, as means to allow students to actively process a range of emotions.

All responses emphasized the necessity of including culturally relevant classrooms. One response highlighted the importance of establishing a space for newcomers. A successful program must address traumas related to immigrating to the United States, and as they begin to transition to a life in a new country with a different dominant culture. It is also important that a program continues to combat culturally held stigmas on mental health. Participants also described that a successful program instills an abundance mindset among Latino students, providing options for activities which encourage students to be active participants: citing possible opportunities of sports, dance, art, and STEM related activities. This is done to allow students to experiment with possible interests and new experiences.

To continue, responses also reported the success that both student and parent workshops can have on the overall mental health experience in elementary school. In terms of student workshops, participants found these as possible ways to provide students with tools which shape success. Workshops aim to educate students on the meaning of emotions and developing a positive sense of self. Parent workshops can also be conducted to improve the community backing of such a program.

One therapist explained the impact that targeted workshops can have on overall involvement. Based on scheduling, workshops can take place during weekends to encourage parents who work during the week to attend. Workshops could also be during weekday mornings, for stay-at-home parents to attend. The goal of these workshops is to combat stigmas, so parents are more willing to allow students to join mental health programs. Participants also cited the importance of bilingual communication with parents to ensure they fully understand what is being asked of them during these workshops.

Potential Funding Options

Given limited funding to elementary schools, when asked of possible ways of funding proposed programs within a framework, most participants discussed grants as a primary means of receiving funds. However, responses acknowledge how lengthy and time-consuming the grant writing process can be. The process can span over months, from writing, to processing, and eventual approval, if chosen to be approved. Participants noted that the process can be meticulous, first beginning with concerns at a school-level, which is then given to a district office, where the grant is typically written. However, funds would not be available until the

following school year, and schools must be very specific as to what resources these funds are allocated towards.

Describing their past experiences in applying for grants, one educator stated, “We are competing with other schools for limited funds”, many times after this difficult and long grant writing process is completed, a school may not even receive the funds requested. Though difficult, one participant did cite a current program that their school has funded through grants, funded at a district-level, which prioritizes the mental health and emotional development of students. If approved, participants expressed the impact that grant money can have as a means of providing students with positive programs aimed towards their success.

One participant noted the possibility of utilizing funding provided through each district’s Local Control and Accountability Plan (LCAP), which provides funding for programs based on community need, to provide students and families with positive mental health resources and services within school sites. Funding decisions are dependent on community advocacy, parents are given the opportunity to speak out and vote on how potential funds are allocated. In their response, one therapist explained the importance of informing parents of the voice they have during these meetings and what role they play in ensuring their students’ success. The therapist had explained that from their own experiences, Latino parents feel that they were unable to participate in these meetings, with parents saying “Pues, ¿yo qué sé?”, “Well, what do I know?”. To combat this, it is important that schools educate parents on the roles they also have in the funding process.

Effects of Covid

All participants shared a common response in their interviews in discussing the need for schools continuing to acknowledge the effects that the Covid-19 pandemic had on students’

mental health. Given the relevance as schools continue to fully transition from online schooling, all participants noted the developmental impacts that the time spent online had on students. Participants reported the need of schools to change student expectations following virtual classes. Possible methods given in responses are through emphasizing socioemotional learning opportunities, allowing students time to be outside. Unstructured play outside of the classroom grants students the opportunity to both remain active, but also be able to continue to develop sociability, engaging with classmates and limiting the amount of isolation, especially considering the impact that quarantine had in each student's social and emotional development.

Discussion

When examining the components of a successful framework based on participant responses, aspects can be organized into three categories: Student Identity, Family Involvement, and Community Resources. All of which revolve around creating a framework which is based on cultural responsiveness and community engagement.

Student Identity

A successful framework incorporates culturally competent and sensitive programs. Relating to the experiences of all participants, two possible programs which can be successful in integrating culture into schools are Enrichment days and Dual Immersion. Enrichment days which highlight students' cultural practices and celebrations allow students to share their own experiences with an entire school through themed assemblies. Recalling that biculturalism is linked to higher educational attainment (Colon & Sanchez 254), enrichment days which

celebrate student culture enable students to develop a multicultural perspective, an important tool which will remain relevant throughout their lives.

Dual Immersion can be beneficial to bilingual students, ensuring that both home language and English are developed throughout their elementary school years. This includes lessons and curriculum following a bilingual approach, but also to be fully successful, requires that communication with families remain consistent with home language. To that point, bilingual programs benefit those who are new to English, or those who wish to learn another language, but in those cases, it is essential that Spanish-speaking families are accommodated and receive communication from schools that they completely understand. Language is an important aspect of student identity and by including it in curriculum, schools can relate lessons to the Latino experience.

Cultural representation is essentially the backbone of a successful framework, one which best supports Latino student mental health. Culture should not only be reflected in the activities, but in the teachers and therapists involved in the program as well. By including teachers and therapists of color, those who share similar backgrounds as students, this is another way that schools can help ensure students are provided culturally competent care and education. Teachers in both Dual Immersion and in fully English classrooms who can integrate home cultures into classrooms help establish a school community built on multiculturalism. Additionally, therapists who understand the experiences of Latino children are best able to provide culturally aware services.

Family Involvement

From the interviews, all participants reported the need to educate parents in order to combat cultural stigmas surrounding mental health, leading to the underutilization of mental health resources. Parent workshops which discuss the role that parents have on their students' lives and mental health. Discussing mental health topics with parents is a way of allowing parents to get involved with schools while developing an understanding of their role in ensuring students receive any needed programs or resources.

First, by focusing on parent's own traumas and teaching them how to deal with their own emotions, the goal of these workshops can be to both promote a positive home life, but also to combat currently held cultural stigmas on mental health, so that student mental health can improve as a result. It is important to note that a school framework that provides mental health programs is built on trust between educators and parents (Langley 250), and these parent workshops are methods of providing parents with more information on the subject, while also teaching positive mental health strategies. Keeping in mind, it is necessary that parents receive communication in home languages when needed to ensure that a trusting relationship is completely established.

Another aspect of family involvement is to allow parents the opportunity to share their own cultures with their students' classes. This can be achieved through family projects, guest speakers, or school-wide events like the previously mentioned enrichments days. These events can all be used to share a family's culture and background to contribute to multiculturalism within an entire school community. DEI groups also grant parents the opportunity to actively promote cultural diversity and representation in schools. This is an excellent way to further strengthen community connections within schools, and the relationships between parents and

educators. While doing so, parent-led DEI groups can strive to further establish schools as a safe environment that represents the entire community.

Community Resources

Providing students and families with available resources is the aspect of this framework which most directly benefits families outside of school. By establishing a Family Coordinator office, schools can ensure that parents are referred to any needed health, social, or economic resources. It is important to acknowledge the different possible pathways that can be offered to parents; based on access to insurance and level of need. It is the responsibility of a Family Coordinator office to maintain communication with both teachers and parents to analyze needs and understand which resources that are available to each family would be most beneficial.

In-house services which should be provided to all students and families are free breakfast and lunch programs, as well as free fruit boxes which can be given to families; both of which to combat food insecurity. Before and after school programs, as well as childcare programs, are methods of schools accommodating for parent's schedules, while being able to offer students more support while parents may still be at work. Transit programs to and from school ensure that students are offered accessible and safe means of getting to school on time.

Health services such as dentist, optometrist, and doctor's visits can be provided at schools and offered to all families within the school community but require coordination between the Family Coordinator office and outside organizations. A Family Coordinator office is then tasked with the responsibilities of actively communicating with both teachers and parents to ensure all needs are being met, while at the same time, forming community connections with partner groups that offer services which can be provided to families both inside and outside of school.

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